

SearchBench: Evaluating Citation Practices in AI-Powered Search Engines

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1. Motivation & Problem Statement

Generative AI search engines are rapidly reshaping how society accesses information (Xu et al. 2023, Suri et al. 2024). Novel search systems are being deployed quickly, but their citation practices remain largely unexamined. In contrast to traditional search engines, AI search engines present LLM-generated summaries of retrieved websites instead of a list of search results. Thereby, the authoritative nature of answers is often hidden from the users, as verifying cited sources requires significant effort. This shift raises serious concerns about information reliability, as recent research finds only 51.5% of generated sentences from existing generative search engines are fully supported with citations (Liu et al. 2023), and suggested references often do not exist or support claims (Zuccon et al. 2023, Wu, Wu, Cassasola, Zhang, Wei, Nguyen, Riantawan, Riantawan, Ho & Zou 2024, Bhattacharyya et al. 2023).

While Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) promises to improve LLM reliability and reduce hallucinations (Shuster et al. 2021, Mallen et al. 2023, Tian et al. 2024), giving LLMs web access does not automatically solve their inherent limitations. RAG systems remain susceptible to factual errors (Hu et al. 2024, Tang & Yang 2024), struggle with long context (Shi et al. 2023, Liu et al. 2024, Li et al. 2024), and can still be misled when information contradicts pre-trained knowledge (Wu, Wu & Zou 2024, Hou et al. 2024, Feldman et al. 2024). Furthermore, the increasing complexity and opacity of search systems threatens transparency and information verification (Shah & Bender 2022), leading scholars to caution against rushing ahead without sufficient study of impacts (Shah & Bender 2024, Venkit et al. 2024).

2. Introducing SearchBench

SearchBench provides the first comprehensive framework for evaluating citation practices and hallucinations across AI search engines through rigorous, replicable metrics. Unlike model-centric evaluations, our novel user-centric benchmark acknowledges that real-world information seeking involves open-ended queries where ground truth might be unavailable or constantly changing.

2.1. Evaluation Metrics

Our framework employs four key metrics for systematic evaluation:

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- Citation precision: fraction of provided citations that actually support their associated Statements
- Citation recall: fraction of citation-worthy claims with proper attribution
- Hallucination score: proportion of responses containing statements not supported by any source
- Plagiarism score: degree of verbatim text extraction from uncited sources

SearchBench relies on an LLM-as-a-judge methodology, which has been thoroughly validated using expert annotation and test sets from prior work (Liu et al. 2023).

2.2. Data

We collected data in three stages:

1. First, we manually selected 2,800 high-impact queries (across seven critical domains health, news, politics, law, governmental services, employment, education), considering real-world datasets including search engine queries (ORCAS (Craswell et al. 2020), Natural Questions (Kwiatkowski et al. 2019)) and chatbot prompts (WildChat (Zhao et al. 2024), LMSYS-Chat 1M (Zheng et al. 2024)).
2. Then, we ran all 2,800 queries on six leading AI search engines (Google AI Overviews, Bing AI Overviews, ChatGPT Search, Perplexity, Gemini, and Copilot). We scraped the AI-generated outputs including the in-text citations, as well as the links to the retrieved sources.
3. Finally, we scraped the content of all references.

2.3. Anticipated Results

The data collection has been completed and will be released publicly. The evaluation is ongoing but will be fully complete by the conference. These findings will provide critical insights for improving information reliability in AI-powered search engines, addressing LLM limitations in citation quality, and informing design recommendations for system developers.

3. Implications

The shifting patterns of citation practices across AI search engines directly impact how users engage with and validate information, potentially transforming how people find and trust online sources. By revealing how these systems attribute (or fail to attribute) information sources, our findings contribute to important discussions about algorithmic accountability and information literacy in an era where AI increasingly mediates between users and the web's knowledge.

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